

Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of Blended Learning Modality

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Abstract:

This descriptive study examined the level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of Blended Learning Modality, in a district, in a medium sized Division in Central Luzon as basis for an Intervention Plan during the School Year 2021-2022. It made use of a reliable self-made questionnaire to collect data from 175 elementary school teachers. The results showed that most teachers were younger and married. Most teachers are older, with higher educational attainment, has a shorter of years in teaching. Teachers registered a moderate level of difficulties in the implementation of the blended learning modality when grouped according to preparation of modules, reinforcement on content delivery, and the interaction with learning facilitators. Teachers obtained a high level of difficulties in the implementation of the blended learning modality in the areas of preparation of modules, reinforcement on content delivery, and the interaction with learning facilitators and when grouped according to age, length of service and highest educational attainment. No significant difference exists in the level difficulties in the implementation of the blended learning modality in the areas of preparation of modules, reinforcement on content delivery, and the interaction with learning facilitators and when grouped according to age, length of service and highest educational attainment.

Keywords: Teachers difficulties, blended learning modality, preparation of modules, reinforcement on content delivery, interaction with learning facilitators.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

When the pandemic strikes, various adaptations are made to deal with the situation. One of the changes is the learning system's process or the way a teacher can continue to teach their learners. Hence, the COVID-19 outbreak has presented numerous challenges for teachers. Because schools were among the institutions affected by the pandemic, the Department of Education is currently adapting to the new normal type of education where parents were given a variety of learning options to ensure that their children's education was not jeopardized. This is a learning delivery method in which learning takes place between a teacher and students who are geographically separated during teaching. Modular Distance Learning (MDL), Online Distance Learning (ODL), and TV/Radio-Based Instruction are the three types of this modality.

On the one hand, in the Philippines, particularly in local settings, blended learning is still relatively new. There are issues and obstacles with this increasing demand for blended learning in public elementary schools that are worth looking into as they obstruct the efficient and effective delivery of teaching and learning. The term "blended learning" describes the blending of traditional classroom instruction with digital online learning. It has been demonstrated that the idea of integrating instructional resources with online intervention enhances both fully online and conventional in-person classes (Alsobhi, 2021). Activity sheets, modules, and printed or digital textbooks are examples of learning resources. Students will have access to these resources whenever it suits them best. The learning materials, weekly home learning plan, study guides, and other resources are created by the teachers and are packaged in high-quality instructional packets that are dropped off and picked up at designated locations where parents, guardians, or para-teachers can meet with the teacher and receive instructions.

As an elementary school teacher in a public school, the researcher saw that despite the promises and obvious advantages of Distance Learning, the learners, parents, and teachers in the whole Philippines have encountered problems with its implementation that need urgent solutions. These problems include the preparation and production, availability of resources, Reinforcement on Content Delivery, and Interaction with learning facilitators. As a result, the researcher felt the drive to conduct this study to determine the level of difficulties teachers face in the implementation of blended learning modality as well as ways to sustain their courage and determination during these trying times.

Current State of Knowledge

Taylor, & et al. (2020) revealed that the problem in distance learning is not where the students are located but in helping them use their time to learn effectively and recall and use the elements for analysis, discussion, and problem-solving. This article explained that although we had already started to use the best possible online resources to support our face-to-face interaction, it also discussed that we could conceptualize the role of the lecturer and give a greater emphasis to their role in developing the individual stage of learning. Lloria et al. (2021) stated in an article that competencies linked to mastery skills in real environments are vital for students' employability. It turned out that because of the COVID-19 pandemic, many teachers have had their teaching responsibilities relocated to non-classroom settings. This setting is considered a primarily disruptive factor to developing multimodal qualities like adaptability, teamwork, and metacognitive and creative problem-solving.

One article published by UNICEF (2020) states that monitoring is important to determine and improve the reach and effectiveness of distance learning modalities. Prolonged school closures have long-term implications and affect some population groups more than others, especially those without access to technology. They also mentioned that feedback from important stakeholders can help improve the quality and efficacy of distance learning modalities: learners, parents/caregivers, and teachers. This implies that those surveys may inquire about their perceptions, preferences, and levels of engagement with different learning modalities. Their article also implied that phone surveys, IVR (Interactive et al.) surveys, and SMS-based surveys are common survey methods that prevent face-to-face interaction during the COVID-19 epidemic. While internet surveys are affordable, they can only reach the online population and are thus not generally advised unless they are used in conjunction with other survey methods that can reach the less advantaged, offline population (Unicef, 2020)

Aviles et al. (2021) explain that support from the school in crafting modules for modular distance learning is very important to make effective and efficient material for effective instructional delivery. It further pointed out that there is no significant difference among teachers' critical challenges and opportunities in modular distance learning delivery. This implies that the participant's profile does not determine their effectiveness. They do not back down in the face of problems in modular distance learning delivery; instead, they push through them. In an article, Vinarao (2021) stated that as schools shift to executing their operations through online platforms, students are no longer allowed to go to school but to sit in front of the screen or face a stack of modules. Some reasons cause learners to suffer in online learning. It could be due to bad internet access. Considering our country's broadband network, participating in virtual classrooms with efficient running is difficult. She added that technical difficulties like system glitches or disconnection can occur in the middle of the class.

Corcuera and Alvarez (2021) explained in an article that a face-to-face teaching and learning environment is still not possible in the Philippine context. This phenomenon leaves the teachers to use various alternative ways of instructional delivery. The abrupt shift in teaching-learning delivery continues to pose challenges for students and teachers who are functioning as educational front-liners throughout the pandemic. In emergency remote education, teachers' lack of sufficient preparation and expertise in online teaching and distance education created educational gaps. Baladjay (2021) stated that the challenges encountered in the implementation of the self-learning modules by teachers were late submission of the accomplished modules, unaccomplished activities in the SLMs, parents' low participation, errors in the content of SLMs, and availability of downloadable SLMs. Baladjay also wrote that the self-learning module is new to all, which resulted in varied challenges. Hence, teachers and learners found adjusting to this new learning modality difficult.

The technological experience of teachers in an online environment is also one of the challenges determining the smoothness of instructional activities. The emphasis on the duties and obligations of teachers in teaching during modular learning, as well as the ability of teachers to understand ICT, have impacted the success of online learning during modular learning. Teachers who do not have online teaching experience or have difficulty running technology and information tools will usually find it challenging to carry out online learning because SFH forces teachers to master a variety of applications. Even teachers with teaching experience or senior teachers can find it difficult to run applications. This condition burdens teachers when implementing instruction, so learning is not optimal. For teachers who master applications, technology tools, and computers, online learning can be an effective instructional method to use during SFH (Rasmitadila et al., 2020).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored to David Perkins's (2007) Theory of difficulty, which stresses the importance of mastering difficult skills and knowledge in order to get to the next level of performance. A robust theory of difficulty identifies learners' common trouble areas in a specific area of instruction and includes a causal account of why they occur, resulting in better teaching and learning. Teachers' responses to recurring challenges in the classroom may fall short. One common approach is to criticize the students' shortcomings and continue teaching in the same manner. Another superior response is to 'teach harder,' devoting more time and attention to specific challenges without

conducting a causal investigation of what causes them to be troublesome. The most effective method is to 'teach smarter,' which is based on a causal analysis developed over time. Building informal ideas of difficulty is an important component of the teaching arts. Hence, a strong theory of difficulty has contributed to increased learning in several studies. The literature on learning and development offers a variety of approaches to comprehending conceptual difficulties, as well as recognizing issues with ritualized knowledge, inert knowledge (knowledge that is too foreign for learners to engage with readily), and tacit knowledge (knowledge that is partly unconscious and poses learning challenges). The aforementioned theory was relevant to the research because it explains how teachers construct what are known as "difficulty or challenge theories." The hypothesis is particularly important in determining the problems faced by the teachers in a district in a medium-sized Division in Central Luzon in providing quality education via distant learning modality.

Objectives

The purpose of this study is to determine the level of difficulties teachers have in the implementation of a blended learning model in a district in a medium-sized division in Central Luzon. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions: 1) level of difficulty of teachers' Blended Learning Modality in terms of the area of preparation of modules, reinforcement on content delivery, interaction with learning facilitators; 2) the level of difficulty teachers have in implementing the blended learning model when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 3) the significant difference in the level of difficulty of teachers in the implementation of the Blended Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design to determine the level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of Blended Learning Modality in a district in a medium-sized school Division in Central Luzon. Descriptive research examines a person's current situation and is commonly utilized in fields such as education, nutrition, epidemiology, and behavioral sciences. Its worth is based on the idea that by observation, analysis, and description, issues can be solved and practices improved. The survey, which comprises questionnaires, personal interviews, phone surveys, and normative surveys, is the most used descriptive research approach (Waiters, 2019). This research design is appropriate for this study because its purpose is to discover elementary teachers' difficulties. This study's nature is to assess the condition of things in their present state. Likewise, it delves into the relationship among variables considered in the study and the influence of one variable on another.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study are the one hundred seventy-five (175) elementary teachers in a district in a medium-sized school Division in Central Luzon. Purposive sampling was used in this study. Purposive sampling, known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the surveys (Alchemer, 2021).

Instruments

This study used a self-made questionnaire to gather the data. The questionnaire is divided into two parts: Part 1 contains queries on respondents' profiles such as age, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

Part 2 is the questionnaire proper with items focused on the level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of Blended Learning Modality in terms of the following areas: Preparation of Modules, Reinforcement on Content Delivery, and Interaction with learning facilitators. This study utilized the Likert Scale rating with 5 as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as rarely, and 1 as almost never. The survey instruments were subjected to validity and reliability test. The validity rating was 4.62, interpreted as "Excellent," which means that the instruments used in this study were valid and the reliability index is 0.977, interpreted as "Excellent," making the instrument reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

The first step in gathering the data needed for this study was to validate the research questionnaire. The questions were validated by three (3) experts in the field. The researcher then obtained a permission letter from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) through the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS). The letter request was distributed to the school head after approval for the second request was obtained. Because face-to-face transactions are discouraged during a health crisis, the researcher used the Google online survey form to

administer the questionnaire. The researcher also provided clear instructions and explained the study's objectives, as well as the terms and items contained in the instruments, so that respondents are fully aware of their responsibilities in answering the tests via phone, text, email, or Facebook messenger, whichever is most convenient for them. After that, the test results and other information were obtained, tallied, tabulated, and interpreted.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and means to determine the difficulty level of teachers' Blended Learning Modality in the following areas: preparation of modules, reinforcement of content delivery, and interaction with learning facilitators.

Objective no. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of difficulty of teachers with blended learning Modalities when grouped according to the aforementioned variables

Objective No.3 used the comparative analytical scheme and m Mann-Whitney U test to determine the level of difficulty of teachers' Blended Learning Modality: when grouped and compared according to variables.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher ensured that the general ethical principles of beneficence, justice, and respect for people were followed to guarantee the study's ethical validity. The participants made the ultimate decision about whether or not to take part in the survey. By using aliases or pseudonyms for the participants' names, the researcher further ensures their confidentiality in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2021. From the researcher's perspective, the participants were literate, working adults with no signs of vulnerability. The researcher also recognized the varied experiences of elementary school teachers in public schools within the framework of the new normal as a social value. Since this study is based on the participants' experiences, they can choose not to answer any questions if doing so would make them uncomfortable. Given the status of the health system today, the researcher and participants closely followed health and safety procedures when distributing the questionnaires.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Preparation of Modules

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...		
1. Reproduction of modules for printed learners.	3.65	High Level
2. Preparing Learning Activity Sheets in case of module shortage	3.65	High Level
3. Having adequate devices to correspond with the reproduction of modules	3.70	High Level
4. Being fair and mindful of my learners' diverse locations and privileges when submitting modules.	3.57	High Level
5. Investing in a fast and reliable internet service provider for uploading modules	3.77	High Level
6. Having basic technological skills.	3.49	Moderate Level
7. Giving learners a considerable amount of time to submit their modules and outputs.	3.66	High Level
8. Having a sufficient number of printed modules for learners.	3.69	High Level
9. Preparing instructional materials for printed learners.	3.73	High Level
10. Developing rubrics for assessment in a clear and concise manner.	3.73	High Level
Overall Mean	3.66	High Level

Table 1 revealed the results of the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in terms of preparation of modules. Generally, there was an overall mean of 3.66, which is interpreted as a high level. Likewise, the details showed that item no. 6, or having basic technological skills, got the lowest mean of 3.49 and is interpreted as a moderate level. On the other hand, the highest mean was obtained for item no. 5, or investing in a fast and reliable internet service provider for uploading modules, and it was interpreted as high level. This result implied that the respondents encountered high difficulty in fast and reliable internet in preparing and uploading the modules for conducting classes. This result was incongruent with the findings of Estella & Löffelholz (2019), revealing that a rise to 62-63% or about 67 million Filipinos have access to the internet and are

thought of as internet users. Accordingly, Kintu et al. (2017) add that users, including teachers, getting into difficulties with technology may result in abandoning the learning and eventual failure of technological applications.

Table 2

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Reinforcement on Content Delivery

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...		
1. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous classes.	3.53	High Level
2. Creating techniques to entice students to take part in online discussions.	3.60	High Level
3. Spending a limited amount of time on distance classes.	3.60	High Level
4. Conducting summative tests, quizzes, and exams online.	3.52	High Level
5. Producing assessment tools in clear and concise manner.	3.64	High Level
6. Having a skill in providing constructive feedback.	3.54	High Level
7. Making a simple analogy for each topic.	3.57	High Level
8. Using common language to present concepts and ideas.	3.55	High Level
9. Developing mastery of skills of learners.	3.65	High Level
10. Enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills among learners	3.66	High Level
Overall Mean	3.58	High Level

Table 2 revealed the results of the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in terms of reinforcement on content delivery. The degree of difficulties encountered by teachers in terms of reinforcement on content delivery obtained an overall mean of 3.58 or a high level. Moreover, the data show that item no. 4, or conducting summative tests, quizzes, and exams online, got the lowest mean among all items in this area. The highest mean of 3.66 was obtained in item no. 10, or enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills among learners at a high level. Thus, these findings inferred that the teachers have high difficulty in reinforcing the content to develop the skills of the students in problem-solving and their metacognitive faculty during the blended learning modality. The findings also describe the results of the study conducted by Ambayon (2020), which found that modular instruction is more operative in the teaching-learning method than usual teaching approaches because, in this modular approach, the students learn in their own stride. Additionally, Sumaoang (2020) emphasized in his study that the main challenge that emerged was a lack of school funding for the production and delivery of modules.

Table 3

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Interaction with Learning Facilitators

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...		
1. Improving teamwork among colleagues.	3.22	Moderate Level
2. Constant communication with co-teachers.	3.18	Moderate Level
3. Sustaining camaraderie along with co-workers.	3.12	Moderate Level
4. Valuing effort in distance learning.	3.25	Moderate Level
5. Showing sympathy with co-teachers having the same problem.	3.21	Moderate Level
6. Accomplishing school roles and responsibilities	3.26	Moderate Level
7. Demonstrating the correct way to solve problems encountered by co-workers	3.24	Moderate Level
8. Complimenting special effort or accomplishments	3.13	Moderate Level
9. Having a skill in providing constructive feedback to co-workers.	3.16	Moderate Level
10. Being fair and mindful of my teachers' diverse locations and privileges.	3.18	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.20	Moderate Level

Table 3 shows the results of the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in terms of interaction with learning facilitators. In general, the level of difficulties teachers had in terms of interaction with learning facilitators was 3.20, or a moderate level. Additionally, the details show that the item no. 3 or sustaining camaraderie along with co-workers got the lowest mean score of 3.12 or a moderate level. On the contrary, item no. 6, or accomplishing school roles and responsibility, got the highest mean score of 3.26, or a moderate level. The results implied that the teachers encountered moderate difficulty in accomplishing school roles and responsibilities during interaction with learning facilitators.

In support of Corcuera and Alvarez's (2021) article, since face-to-face teaching and learning environment is still not possible in the Philippine context, this phenomenon leaves the teachers to use various alternative ways of

instructional delivery. The abrupt shift in teaching-learning delivery continues to pose challenges for not just students but also teachers who are functioning as educational front-liners throughout the pandemic. In the context of emergency remote education, teachers' lack of sufficient preparation and expertise in online teaching and distance education created educational gaps.

Table 4

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Preparation of Modules When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Reproduction of modules for printed learners.	3.58	High Level	3.72	High Level
2. Preparing Learning Activity Sheets in case of module shortage	3.61	High Level	3.69	High Level
3. Having adequate devices to correspond with the reproduction of modules	3.65	High Level	3.74	High Level
4. Being fair and mindful of my learners' diverse locations and privileges when submitting modules.	3.58	High Level	3.57	High Level
5. Investing in a fast and reliable internet service provider for uploading modules	3.80	High Level	3.75	High Level
6. Having basic technological skills.	3.34	Moderate Level	3.61	High Level
7. Giving learners a considerable amount of time to submit their modules and outputs.	3.60	High Level	3.72	High Level
8. Having sufficient number of printed modules for learners.	3.69	High Level	3.70	High Level
9. Preparing instructional materials for printed learners.	3.6	High Level	3.80	High Level
10. Developing rubrics for assessment in clear and concise manner.	3.69	High Level	3.76	High Level
Mean	3.62	High Level	3.71	High Level

Table 4 shows the results of the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in terms of the preparation of modules when grouped according to age. Moreover, the data revealed that there was a high level of difficulty in the implementation of blended learning modality in terms of the preparation of modules, as obtained by the younger and older age groups, with an overall mean of 3.62 and 3.71, respectively. Additionally, the results also revealed that younger age group obtained the lowest mean of 3.34 or a moderate level in item no. 6 or having basic technological skills, while the older age group got the lowest mean of 3.57 or a high level in item no. 4 or being fair and mindful of my learners' diverse locations and privileges when submitting modules. On the other hand, the younger age group obtained its highest mean of 3.80 in item no. 5, or Investing in a fast and reliable internet service provider for uploading modules, which is interpreted as a high level. Likewise, the older age group got the highest mean of 3.80 or a high level in item no. 9 or preparing instructional materials for printed learners. These results implied that in preparing modules, the age group differs in the difficulty encountered. The younger group was challenged to have a fast and reliable internet provider, while the older group found difficulty in preparing instructional materials, perhaps due to a lack of equipment.

Table 5

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Preparation of Modules When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Reproduction of modules for printed learners.	3.68	High Level	3.61	High Level
2. Preparing Learning Activity Sheets in case of module shortage	3.66	High Level	3.64	High Level
3. Having adequate devices to correspond with reproduction of modules	3.77	High Level	3.58	High Level

4. Being fair and mindful of my learners' diverse locations and privileges when submitting modules.	3.7	High Level	3.36	Moderate Level
5. Investing in a fast and reliable internet service provider for uploading of modules	3.9	High Level	3.56	High Level
6. Having basic technological skills.	3.49	Moderate Level	3.49	Moderate Level
7. Giving learners considerable amount of time to submit their modules and outputs.	3.79	High Level	3.46	Moderate Level
8. Having sufficient number of printed modules for learners.	3.81	High Level	3.49	Moderate Level
9. Preparing instructional materials for printed learners.	3.79	High Level	3.63	High Level
10. Developing rubrics for assessment in clear and concise manner.	3.78	High Level	3.64	High Level
Mean	3.73	High Level	3.55	High Level

Table 5 shows the data on the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of preparation of modules when grouped according to length of service. Generally, the shorter length of service obtained an overall mean of 3.73, and the longer length of service got 3.55, which was interpreted as a high level. In addition, the shorter length of service got the lowest mean of 3.49 or a moderate level in item no. 6 or having basic technological skills. While the longer length of service obtained the lowest mean of 3.36 or a moderate level in item no. 4, or being fair and mindful of my learners' diverse locations and privileges when submitting modules. On the other hand, the shorter length of service got the highest mean of 3.90 or a high level in item no. 5 or Investing in a fast and reliable internet service provider for uploading of modules. The longer length of service got the highest mean of 3.64 or a high level in item no. 2, or preparing Learning Activity Sheets in case of module shortage and ten or developing rubrics for assessment in a clear and concise manner. Thus, these results inferred that tenured or not; there was difficulty encountered in preparing modules, especially in reliable internet and backup learning activities and rubrics for assessment.

Table 6

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Preparation of Modules When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Reproduction of modules for printed learners.	3.69	High Level	3.62	High Level
2. Preparing Learning Activity Sheets in case of module shortage	3.68	High Level	3.63	High Level
3. Having adequate devices to correspond with reproduction of modules	3.76	High Level	3.65	High Level
4. Being fair and mindful of my learners' diverse locations and privileges when submitting modules.	3.59	High Level	3.56	High Level
5. Investing in a fast and reliable internet service provider for uploading of modules	3.71	High Level	3.82	High Level
6. Having basic technological skills.	3.53	High Level	3.45	Moderate Level
7. Giving learners considerable amount of time to submit their modules and outputs.	3.73	High Level	3.61	High Level
8. Having sufficient number of printed modules for learners.	3.72	High Level	3.67	High Level
9. Preparing instructional materials for printed learners.	3.71	High Level	3.74	High Level
10. Developing rubrics for assessment in clear and concise manner	3.78	High Level	3.68	High Level
Mean	3.69	High Level	3.64	High Level

Table 6 presented the results on the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of preparation of modules when grouped according to highest educational attainment. In general, the lower educational attainment got an overall mean of 3.69, and the higher educational attainment got 3.64, which was interpreted as a high level. In detail, the respondents with lower educational attainment and higher educational attainment obtained the lowest mean of 3.53 or high level and 3.45 or moderate level, respectively. Contrastingly, the lower educational attainment attained the highest mean of 3.78 or a high level in item no. 10 or developing rubrics for assessment in a clear and concise manner. Likewise, the higher educational attainment attained the highest mean of 3.82 or a high level in item no. 5 or Investing in a fast and reliable internet service provider for uploading of modules. These results suggested that regardless of educational

attainment, difficulty occurs in preparing modules, such as crafting a basis for assessments that is clear and concise and possessing fast and uninterrupted internet.

Table 7

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Reinforcement on Content Delivery When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous classes.	3.46	Moderate Level	3.58	High Level
2. Creating techniques to entice students to take part in online discussions.	3.56	High Level	3.62	High Level
3. Spending a limited amount of time on distance classes.	3.60	High Level	3.59	High Level
4. Conducting summative tests, quizzes, and exams online.	3.50	High Level	3.54	High Level
5. Producing assessment tools in clear and concise manner.	3.60	High Level	3.68	High Level
6. Having a skill in providing constructive feedback.	3.51	High Level	3.57	High Level
7. Making a simple analogy for each topic.	3.56	High Level	3.57	High Level
8. Using common language to present concepts and ideas.	3.51	High Level	3.58	High Level
9. Developing mastery of skills of learners.	3.60	High Level	3.70	High Level
10. Enhancing metacognitive and creative problem solving skills among learners	3.60	High Level	3.71	High Level
Mean	3.55	High Level	3.61	High Level

Table 7 revealed the results of the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of reinforcement on content delivery when grouped according to age. Generally, the younger group obtained an overall mean of 3.55 or a high level, and the older group got 3.61 or a high level. Moreover, the details showed that the younger age group got the lowest mean of 3.46 or a moderate level in item no. 1 or Simplifying concepts during asynchronous classes. Likewise, the older age group got the lowest mean of 3.54 or a high level in item no. 4 or Conducting summative tests, quizzes, and exams online. Consequently, the highest mean obtained by the younger age group was 3.60, or a high level in item no. 3 or Spending a limited amount of time on distance classes, 5 or Producing assessment tools in a clear and concise manner, 9 or Developing mastery of skills of learners, and 10 or Enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills among learners. Likewise, the older age group achieved the highest mean of 3.71 or a high level in item no. 10 or Enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills among learners. These findings suggested that, whether young or old, difficulties in reinforcing blended modality were apparent in terms of spending time online, establishing assessments, ensuring skills mastery, and enhancing creative problem-solving skills among learners.

Table 8

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Reinforcement on Content Delivery When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous classes.	3.56	High Level	3.47	Moderate Level
2. Creating techniques to entice students to take part in online discussions.	3.62	High Level	3.55	High Level
3. Spending a limited amount of time on distance classes.	3.62	High Level	3.55	High Level
4. Conducting summative tests, quizzes, and exams online.	3.53	High Level	3.50	High Level
5. Producing assessment tools in clear and concise manner.	3.68	High Level	3.58	High Level
6. Having a skill in providing constructive feedback.	3.60	High Level	3.44	Moderate Level
7. Making a simple analogy for each topic.	3.63	High Level	3.46	Moderate Level
8. Using common language to present concepts and ideas.	3.60	High Level	3.46	Moderate Level
9. Developing mastery of skills of learners.	3.69	High Level	3.6	High Level
10. Enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills among learners	3.70	High Level	3.58	High Level

Mean	3.62	High Level	3.52	High Level
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Table 8 presented the data on the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of reinforcement on content delivery when grouped according to length of service. In general, the shorter length of service obtained an overall mean of 3.62 or a high level, while the longer length of service got an overall mean of 3.52 or a high level. Additionally, the details showed that the shorter length of service got the lowest mean of 3.53 or a high level in item no. 4 or Conducting summative tests, quizzes, and exams online, and the longer length of service got the lowest mean of 3.44 or a moderate level in item no. 6 or Having a skill in providing constructive feedback. Contrastingly, the shorter length of service got the highest mean of 3.70 or a high level in item no. 10 or Enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills among learners, and the longer length of service got 3.60 or a high level in item no. 9 or developing mastery of skills of learners. These data implied that despite the length of service, the difficulty in reinforcing content delivery for blended learning modality was high, especially in terms of enhancing learners' cognitive ability and mastery of skills.

Table 9

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Reinforcement on Content Delivery When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Simplifying concepts during asynchronous classes.	3.64	High Level	3.44	Moderate Level
2. Creating techniques to entice students to take part in online discussions.	3.65	High Level	3.55	High Level
3. Spending a limited amount of time on distance classes.	3.67	High Level	3.54	High Level
4. Conducting summative tests, quizzes, and exams online.	3.59	High Level	3.47	Moderate Level
5. Producing assessment tools in clear and concise manner.	3.73	High Level	3.57	High Level
6. Having a skill in providing constructive feedback.	3.60	High Level	3.50	High Level
7. Making a simple analogy for each topic.	3.67	High Level	3.49	Moderate Level
8. Using common language to present concepts and ideas.	3.64	High Level	3.48	Moderate Level
9. Developing mastery of skills of learners.	3.71	High Level	3.61	High Level
10. Enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills among learners	3.73	High Level	3.60	High Level
Mean	3.66	High Level	3.53	High Level

Table 9 presented the results of the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of reinforcement on content delivery when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Generally, the lower educational attainment obtained an overall mean of 3.66 or a high level, and the higher educational attainment got an overall mean of 3.53, which is interpreted as a high level. In details, the lower educational attainment got the lowest mean of 3.59 or a high level in item no. 4 or Conducting summative tests, quizzes, and exams online. Meanwhile, higher educational attainment obtained the lowest mean of 3.44 or a moderate level in item no. 1 or simplifying concepts during asynchronous classes. On the other hand, the highest mean obtained by the lowest educational attainment was 3.73 or a high level in items no. 5 or producing assessment tools in a clear and concise manner and no. 10 or Enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills, and the higher educational attainment got the highest mean of 3.61 or a high level in item no. 9 or Developing mastery of skills of learners. These findings inferred that regardless of educational attainment, there was a high difficulty in reinforcing content delivery on a blended learning modality, particularly in providing clear and concise assessment tools, enhancing cognitive ability, and developing skills mastery.

Table 10

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Interaction with Learning Facilitators When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Improving teamwork among colleagues.	3.07	Moderate Level	3.36	Moderate Level
2. Constant communication with co-teachers.	3.08	Moderate Level	3.27	Moderate Level
3. Sustaining camaraderie along with co-workers.	3.01	Moderate Level	3.22	Moderate Level

4. Valuing effort in distance learning.	3.04	Moderate Level	3.43	Moderate Level
5. Showing sympathy with co-teachers having the same problem.	3.06	Moderate Level	3.34	Moderate Level
6. Accomplishing school roles and responsibilities	3.16	Moderate Level	3.36	Moderate Level
7. Demonstrating the correct way to solve problems encountered with co-workers	3.08	Moderate Level	3.37	Moderate Level
8. Complimenting special efforts or accomplishments	3.06	Moderate Level	3.20	Moderate Level
9. Having a skill in providing constructive feedback to co-workers.	3.04	Moderate Level	3.26	Moderate Level
10. Being fair and mindful of my teachers' diverse locations and privileges.	3.13	Moderate Level	3.22	Moderate Level
Mean	3.07	Moderate Level	3.30	Moderate Level

Table 10 projected the results of the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of interaction with learning facilitators when grouped according to age. In general, the younger age group obtained an overall mean of 3.07 or a moderate level, and the older age group got an overall mean of 3.30, which is interpreted as a moderate level. In detail, the lowest mean attained by the younger age group was 3.01, or a moderate level in item no. 3 or sustaining camaraderie along with co-workers, while older age group got 3.20 or a moderate level in item no. 8 or complimenting special effort or accomplishments. On the other hand, the highest mean obtained by the younger age group was 3.16 or a moderate level in item no. 6 or accomplishing school roles and responsibilities. Likewise, the older age group got 3.37 or a moderate level in item no. 7 or demonstrating the correct way to solve problems encountered by co-workers. These results implied that age groups have difficulty interacting with learning facilitators, particularly in accomplishing roles and responsibilities and in demonstrating problem-solving solutions.

Table 11

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Interaction with Learning Facilitators When Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Improving teamwork among colleagues.	3.29	Moderate Level	3.12	Moderate Level
2. Constant communication with co-teachers.	3.31	Moderate Level	2.96	Moderate Level
3. Sustaining camaraderie along with co-workers.	3.21	Moderate Level	2.96	Moderate Level
4. Valuing effort in distance learning.	3.3	Moderate Level	3.18	Moderate Level
5. Showing sympathy with co-teachers having the same problem.	3.28	Moderate Level	3.09	Moderate Level
6. Accomplishing school roles and responsibilities	3.37	Moderate Level	3.09	Moderate Level
7. Demonstrating the correct way to solve problems encountered by co-workers	3.32	Moderate Level	3.09	Moderate Level
8. Complimenting special efforts or accomplishments	3.25	Moderate Level	2.93	Moderate Level
9. Having a skill in providing constructive feedback to co-workers.	3.27	Moderate Level	2.98	Moderate Level
10. Being fair and mindful of my teachers' diverse locations and privileges.	3.30	Moderate Level	2.96	Moderate Level
Mean	3.29	Moderate Level	3.04	Moderate Level

Table 11 shows the results on the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in The Area of Interaction with Learning Facilitators When Grouped According to Length of Service. Generally, there was an overall mean of 3.29 or a moderate level, obtained by the shorter length of service, and the longer length of service got 3.04 or a moderate level. Moreover, the details show that the lowest mean obtained by the shorter length of service was 3.21 or a moderate level in item no. 3 or sustaining camaraderie along with co-workers, and the longer length of service got 2.93 or a moderate level in item no. 8 or complimenting special effort or accomplishments. On the other hand, the highest mean attained by the shorter length of service was 3.37 or a moderate level in item no. 6 or accomplishing school roles and responsibility. While, the longer length of service got the highest mean of 3.18 or a moderate level in item no. 4 or valuing effort in distance learning. These findings implied that the teachers' length of service determined the difficulties in the implementation of the blended learning modality especially in interaction with learning facilitators, particularly in accomplishing responsibilities and valuing effort in distance learning.

Table 12

Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area of Interaction with Learning Facilitators When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulties in...				
1. Improving teamwork among colleagues.	3.21	Moderate Level	3.24	Moderate Level
2. Constant communication with co-teachers.	3.28	Moderate Level	3.11	Moderate Level
3. Sustaining camaraderie along with co-workers.	3.21	Moderate Level	3.06	Moderate Level
4. Valuing effort in distance learning.	3.30	Moderate Level	3.22	Moderate Level
5. Showing sympathy with co-teachers having the same problem.	3.18	Moderate Level	3.23	Moderate Level
6. Accomplishing school roles and responsibilities	3.23	Moderate Level	3.29	Moderate Level
7. Demonstrating the correct way to solve problems encountered by co-workers	3.30	Moderate Level	3.19	Moderate Level
8. Complimenting special efforts or accomplishments	3.18	Moderate Level	3.10	Moderate Level
9. Having a skill in providing constructive feedback to co-workers.	3.18	Moderate Level	3.15	Moderate Level
10. Being fair and mindful of my teachers' diverse locations and privileges.	3.17	Moderate Level	3.19	Moderate Level
Mean	3.22	Moderate Level	3.17	Moderate Level

Table 12 reveals the data on the level of difficulties teachers experience in the implementation of the blended learning model in the area of interaction with learning facilitators when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Generally, there was an overall mean of 3.22 or a moderate level obtained by the lower educational attainment, and the higher educational attainment got 3.17, which was interpreted as a moderate level. Additionally, the details showed that the lower educational attainment got the lowest mean of 3.17 or a moderate level in item no. 10 or Being Fair and Mindful of My Teachers' diversity, while the higher educational attainment got 3.06 or a moderate level in item no. 3 or Sustaining camaraderie along with co-workers. Contrastingly, the highest mean obtained by the lower educational attainment was 3.30, or a moderate level in items no. 4, or Valuing effort in distance learning, and 7, or Demonstrating the correct way to solve problems encountered with co-workers. Likewise, the higher educational attainment got the highest mean of 3.29 or a moderate level in item no. 6 or Accomplishing school roles and responsibility. Further, the results suggested that teachers' educational attainment encountered difficulties in demonstrating the proper way to solve problems, valuing efforts, and in accomplishing roles and responsibilities in interacting with learning facilitators.

Table 13

Difference in the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area Preparation of Modules When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	81	84.84	3551.0	0.443	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	94	90.72				
Length of Service	Shorter	110	90.07	3347.0	0.480	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	65	84.49				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	76	88.43	3729.0	0.921	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	99	87.67				

Table 13 revealed the results of the difference in the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of preparation of modules when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. The data showed that Age (u-value-3551.0), Length of Service (3347.0), and Highest Educational Attainment (u-value-3729.0) obtained a p-value of 0.443, 0.480, and 0.921 that were higher than the p-value of 0.05. Thus, the results showed no significance. Further, the findings infer that the teacher's age, length of service, and the highest educational attainment do not significantly affect the difficulties encountered in the conduct of blended learning modality, particularly in preparing modules. The results conform to the study of Aguilay and Ebal (2021), which stated that there is no significant difference in the perceived difficulties of modular distance learning implementation as to the Production and Printing of Modules when grouped when grouped

according to teacher-respondents' profile variables. Yet it does not conform to the study of Ismail and Rozita (2018), who stated that teachers' variables such as age and teaching experiences have a certain impact on teacher effectiveness in distance learning.

Table 14

Difference in the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area Reinforcement on Content Delivery When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	81	86.49	3685.0	0.714	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	94	89.30				
Length of Service	Shorter	110	89.84	3372.5	0.530		Not Significant
	Longer	65	84.88				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	76	91.19	3519.5	0.464	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	99	85.55				

Table 14 presented the data on the difference in the Level of Difficulty of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of reinforcement on content delivery when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. The results revealed that age (U-test value-3685.0) got a p-value of 0.714, while the length of service (U-test value-3372.5) got 0.530, and the highest educational attainment (U-test value-3519.5) got 0.464. Moreover, all of the obtained p-values were higher than the significance level of 0.05; thus, they were not significant. These findings suggested that age, length of service, and the highest educational attainment do not have differences in the difficulty encountered in terms of reinforcement on content delivery in the blended learning modality. The findings are in harmony with Jayani (2021), who stated that there is no significant difference in perception of the challenges encountered during the modular distance learning approach when the data are grouped according to teachers' profiles. Thus, the data suggests that the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 15

Difference in the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the Area Interaction with Learning Facilitators When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	81	84.14	3494.0	0.346	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	94	91.33				
Length of Service	Shorter	110	91.25	3218.0	0.267		Not Significant
	Longer	65	82.51				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	76	89.02	3684.5	0.814	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	99	87.22				

Table 15 shows the results of the difference in the Level of Difficulties of Teachers in the Implementation of the Blended Learning Modality in the area of interaction with learning facilitators when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Additionally, the data disclosed that age (U-test value 3494.0) and a p-value of 0.346. Also, the length of service (U test value- 3218.0) and a p-value of 0.267, and the highest educational attainment (U test value-3218.0) and p-value of 0.267. Further, all p-values were higher than the significant value of 0.05. Thus, there were no significant differences. Moreover, age, length of service, and the highest educational attainment do not have significant differences encountered in the implementation of blended learning modality in terms of interaction with the learning facilitators. The findings somewhat conform to Resoor's (2023) study, which examined and identified the challenges encountered by the teachers. The study results revealed that there is no significant difference between the degree of challenges encountered by the respondents when grouped and compared according to selected variables such as age, sex, civil status, and highest educational attainment.

Conclusions:

Based on the summary of the findings, the researcher draws the following conclusions: It was established that the teachers encountered difficulties in the implementation of the blended learning modality, particularly in the preparation of modules and reinforcement of content delivery. On the other hand, teachers' interaction with the learning facilitators during the blended learning modality was moderately difficult.

Additionally, it was established that regardless of teachers' age, tenure, and educational attainment, the preparation of modules, the reinforcement of content delivery, and the interaction with learning facilitators faced a high challenge in the implementation of blended learning.

Further, it was concluded that the challenges in the preparation of modules, reinforcement on content delivery, and the interaction with learning facilitators do not significantly differ in terms of age, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are advanced: It was recommended that the Principal of the school, through the approval of PSDS, SDS, and the budget officer, allocate the budget to fast and reliable Internet. Likewise, the Principal may also create a letter requesting the LGU's assistance with regard to the internet connection. This would be a great assistance for them in being able to fulfill their duties much better than before. This would give them great ease in downloading and uploading files/modules/reports via the Internet. Great online performance surely awaits. A fund-raising activity conducted by the PTA or other stakeholders may also be recommended to provide a stable and fast internet connection.

School Principals may encourage teachers to take post-graduate programs related to their field of specialization before or during the school year. Also, it was highly suggested that the Principal, together with the District Supervisors and Curriculum Implementers, should create technical working groups and coaching sessions before the school calendar to strengthen the teachers' capacity to implement blended learning modality, particularly in the reinforcement of content delivery, specifically in enhancing metacognitive and creative problem-solving skills among learners.

Moreover, it was proposed that Public School District Supervisors and the Principal should formulate and design a program that would address the challenges encountered by the teachers in their work. The school principal may also create a program to recognize those teachers who rendered their service willingly and those who fulfilled their duties. This program may be entitled "Teacher, Ikaw na! The Best Ka!" so that teachers will be motivated and inspired to accomplish their work on time. Service credits may also be given by the division office to motivate the teachers further.

This study also suggested that in order to address difficulties in all areas, teachers—whether new hires or seasoned pros—should receive ongoing training.

Acknowledgment

The researcher would like to express her deepest gratitude to the all people whose guidance, expertise, and unwavering support have been invaluable throughout the entirety of this research endeavor. Their mentorship has shaped not only the direction of this research but also the growth of the researcher. To the researcher's family for their unwavering belief, support and understanding throughout this academic pursuit, to the closest friends and colleagues who in one way or another being there in full support right from the start of the study until this point.

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